

**whorl
16**

42 light/dark increments counted
Average increment width = 56 µm
Total time in section = 25.6 d
Average duration of increment = 0.61 d

89 * 5 = 445 light/dark increments counted
Average increment width = 9.5 µm
If same increments, then total time = 271 d

